

Preparation and Analysis of Information Security Events for Deep Learning Models in University Networks

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This article looks at modern cybersecurity methods in educational institutions, using a university with a developed IT infrastructure as an example. The relevance of this work is determined by the growing number of cyberattacks on educational institutions' networks and the need to implement smart information protection systems. A number of typical threats are considered, including unauthorized access, malware, and phishing, as well as the characteristics of the university infrastructure that affect the risk of cybersecurity incidents.

The object of this study is deep learning methods applied to the analysis of information security events and the detection of malicious activity. Approaches to normalizing operating system and application event logs are proposed to ensure data unification, as well as a method for vectorizing events by highlighting key features to prepare high-quality input data for deep learning algorithms. The proposed architecture of the information protection system based on explainable deep learning includes modules for collecting and normalizing events, vectorizing them, analyzing them using neural networks, and visualizing the results.

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1. Introduction

The educational environment today is focused on integrating digital technologies, including cloud platforms, online courses, distance learning systems, electronic libraries, and databases [1]. These components form a complex information technology (IT) infrastructure, leading to an increase in the number and complexity of cyberattacks.

Educational institutions are an attractive target for attackers, partly because they hold significant assets of various kinds that are attractive to cybercriminals: personal data of students, employees, and applicants; scientific

research; administrative documents; financial reports; and computing resources. Disruption of IT infrastructure will result in not only information loss for educational institutions, but also reputational and economic damage.

The focus of threats in the educational information environment differs from the targets in other sectors. For example, in the banking sector, the main focus is on protecting transactions and complying with strict regulatory requirements [2], while in industry, the focus is on ensuring the stability of technological processes and the security of automated production management systems [3]. In universities, the IT infrastructure is more distributed and dynamic: physically remote buildings are combined with a central building, and there is a need for remote access to system resources, including laboratory stands and distance learning platforms [4]. A

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problem in ensuring cybersecurity in higher education institutions is the high proportion of temporary users, which complicates the management of access to IT infrastructure and the control of information flows.

The specific features of the information infrastructure of higher education institutions as objects of protection include the following:

- High degree of openness and user diversity. Educational networks provide access to a large number of users, including students, instructors, and external researchers, using guest access via Wi-Fi and cloud resources, which increases the risk of unauthorized intrusion.
- Heterogeneity and uncontrollability of end devices. In an educational environment, access to IT infrastructure is provided not only from workstations managed and administered by the university, but also from personal laptops, smartphones, tablets, and IoT devices, which expands the attack perimeter and complicates the implementation of uniform information security policies.
- Diversity of services. The educational infrastructure simultaneously operates a learning management system (LMS), electronic journals, student personal data storage systems, scientific databases, and online testing resources, each of which has specific vulnerabilities.
- Large volumes of personal data. Higher education institutions process student and employee data (names, passport details, grades, medical information) in their IT infrastructure, making them an attractive target for attackers.
- Limited resources for protection. In contrast to commercial organizations, higher education institutions have limited cybersecurity budgets, which requires the use of cost-effective solutions.

Traditional security methods based on signature mechanisms are proving insufficiently effective against modern threats that use social engineering techniques, targeted attacks on IT infrastructure, and exploitation of zero-day vulnerabilities. Another particular problem in ensuring information security in higher education institutions is the shortage of qualified personnel, which reduces the effectiveness of incident response and increases the risk of successful attacks [5]. This creates a need to introduce intelligent cyber security analysis systems into the IT infrastructure of educational institutions, capable of detecting anomalies, predicting possible incidents, and generating explainable solutions for information security system operators [6].

One of the areas in this field is deep learning (DL) methods. It should be noted that the main drawback of these methods is the black box principle, which makes it impossible to interpret the decisions made by the model [7]. To overcome this drawback, explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) approaches are used to increase the transparency, trustworthiness, and accuracy of information security systems.

The object of this article is to develop an architecture for an educational institution's information security system based on a modular approach, as well as a method for normalizing and vectorizing information security events.

2. Typical security threats in the IT infrastructure of universities

The IT infrastructure of higher education institutions includes a variety of elements: server clusters, data storage systems, student and faculty databases, web portals, cloud services, internal networks and wireless access, electronic document management systems, as well as elements of the Internet of Things (IoT), including access control and video surveillance systems [8, 9]. Such a multi-component infrastructure significantly expands the surface area for cyberattacks by attackers.

Based on reports on cyber threats for 2025 from companies such as Positive Technologies, F6, Palo Alto Network, Kaspersky, and others, we have identified the following main types of attacks [10, 11]:

- Targeted attacks focused on unauthorized access to the personal data of students and employees, research results, and the organization's management systems.
- Attacks using malicious software (malware) carried out through phishing emails, the introduction of Trojan programs and ransomware, which is the initial point of compromise for the network and allows malware to spread throughout the IT infrastructure.
- Insider threats. Insufficient digital literacy among staff, failure to comply with basic cyber hygiene principles, and deliberate actions by dishonest employees or students create the risk of confidential information leaks and internal abuse.
- Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks aimed at disrupting web resources and online services during peak loads - during admission campaigns, exam sessions, and remote forms of assessment.
- Attacks on cloud services and external digital platforms (e.g., Google Workspace, Microsoft 365, Dropbox, Mail.ru). Vulnerabilities in application programming interfaces, incorrect configuration of access policies, and insufficient control over the distribution of user rights can lead to data compromise outside the perimeter of the university's local network.
- Zero-day attacks and existing vulnerabilities. Given the low level of vulnerability management in higher education institutions, outdated operating systems and applications remain in use, there are no regulations for controlling

network ports, and software updates are not performed in a timely manner. All of this significantly increases the probability of a successful attack.

The collection of these types of attacks requires the creation of a flexible and adaptive defense system capable not only of recording incidents, but also of predicting possible attacks before they are exploited. One of the current areas of development for such intelligent systems is the use of XAI algorithms, which are also capable of providing transparent explanations of their results (predictions).

3. Deep learning methods and models in cybersecurity

Information security event logs can generate around a million events per day, so it is necessary to use tools that can process large amounts of data, identify hidden patterns, and perform complex classification and prediction tasks. Such tools include technologies based on DL algorithms. For example, DL models are successfully used to detect network traffic anomalies, identify malicious activity, classify incidents, and predict potential threats [12].

Information security event logs can generate around a million events per day, so it is necessary to use a tool that can process large amounts of data, identify hidden patterns, and perform complex classification and prediction tasks. One such tool is DL technology. For example, DL models are used to detect network traffic anomalies, identify malicious activity, classify incidents, and predict potential threats.

The choice of DL model architecture is determined by the structure of the analyzed data and the nature of the attacks. In the field of cybersecurity, the following DL models are most widely used [7, 12]:

- Convolutional neural networks (CNN) used to analyze network packets, visualize user behavior, and detect patterns of malicious activity.

- Recurrent neural networks (RNN) and their modifications (LSTM, GRU) effective in sequence analysis tasks, such as tracking temporal changes in user activity or network connections.
- Autoencoders used to detect anomalies by restoring normal system behavior and evaluating deviations from it.
- Graph neural networks (GNN) used to analyze complex relationships between objects, such as between IP addresses, ports, and protocols within a single incident.
- Unification of data formats.
- Reduction of information noise from information security events.
- Creation of a database for correlation.
- Ensuring the completeness and contextuality of the data set.
- Prioritization of response.

For practical application of these models, it is necessary to clearly define the structure of the input data and the format of the events to be analyzed. A distinctive feature of the proposed approach is that user network activity is analyzed using operating system event logs, such as "Security", "Applications" and others.

4. Normalization of information security events

For correct model training, as well as for the integration of XAI mechanisms, a formalized representation of events is necessary. This is especially important in environments where the security system operator requires not just a signal about an anomaly, but an interpretable explanation of the detected deviation.

Event logs from operating systems, network equipment, application software, and specialized security tools represent heterogeneous information flows characterized by differences in data format, structure, and semantics. Effective incident detection and correlation analysis are impossible without unifying this data. In this context, event normalization becomes a critical process, understood as bringing different types of messages into a single representation suitable for centralized analysis.

The main goals of event normalization are as follows:

Normalization is a prerequisite for the functioning of security information and event management (SIEM) systems and serves as the basis for implementing threat hunting scenarios and threat analysis. Methodologically, the normalization process includes a series of complementary stages, as described below.

Methodologically, the normalization process includes a number of complementary steps. The first step involves format and structural data alignment. Events received in various formats (text syslog records, JSON structures, XML documents, as well as proprietary representations) are converted into standardized exchange schemas, such as Common Event Format (CEF), Log Event Extended Format (LEEF), or Intrusion Detection Message Exchange Format (IDMEF), with mandatory attributes timestamp, event source, action subject, impact object, and operation result.

The next stage involves semantic normalization. Systems use different terms for identical actions (e.g., "logon", "login" and "authentication success"), so it is necessary to bring them into a common terminological model, i.e., to match events with unified categories and taxonomies, in accordance with universal models, including MITRE ATT&CK [13]. This stage facilitates the interpretation of events and their use in analytical procedures.

The next necessary step is to synchronize timestamps. In a multi-system environment, there are discrepancies in time zones and event recording formats, which distorts the sequence of attack actions. Therefore, timestamps should be brought to a single standard (in

one time zone) and centralized synchronization mechanisms (NTP protocol) should be used to increase the reliability of incident reconstruction.

The next step is to add additional information to information security events. IP addresses should be converted into geolocation and organization affiliation data, unique user identifiers should be correlated with names, and system entities should be correlated with configuration database data. The research conducted in this work has shown that the introduction of this stage reduces the level of false positives and increases the accuracy of correlation scenarios.

In order to standardize the criticality of events, we use the following five-level scale: 0 - Informational, 1 - Low, 2 - Medium, 3 - High, 4 - Critical.

When selecting information security event attributes in this work, the following principles were identified as a result of analyzing possible options:

- completeness of the description of the action (subject, object, time, place, and nature of the impact);
- unification;
- suitability of data for intellectual analysis (data must be converted into numerical format for subsequent analysis).

4.1. Normalization of the event log of information operating systems (OS)

At the OS level, events reflecting user and process activity are analyzed. The following OS events are selected as significant events that indicate the possibility of an attack:

- process launch:
C:\Users\Student\AppData\Local\Temp\Name1.exe;
- system file modification:
C:\Windows\System32\config\SAM;

- failed login attempts: 5 failed attempts to log into Windows with a student account;
- creation of a new account: adding temp_admin via PowerShell;
- application installation: unknown keylog installed via MSI package.

It should be noted that the events listed may correspond to both legitimate activity and potential threats. In addition, events recorded at the OS level are characterized by a high degree of heterogeneity in terms of representation formats and semantics: actions that are identical in meaning (e.g., starting a process or changing a system file) can be recorded by different sources with different attributes. As a result, it is necessary to bring OS events into a uniform format for subsequent analysis and to reduce the amount of stored data.

For the above events, taking into account typical techniques and tactics of the attacker in accordance with the MITRE ATT&CK model [13], we form the following structure of a normalized feature vector:

$$e_i = (EventID, IDProc, User, Type, File, dir, Time) \quad (1)$$

where EventID is the Windows event code (4625, 4688, 4670, etc.), IDproc is the unique process identifier, User is the account that initiated the event, Type is the type of operation (starting a process, changing a file, creating a user), File is the executable file or modifiable resource, dir is the binary flag for critical directories (System32, AppData, Program Files), Time is the date and time of the event.

For the event launch of the process Name1.exe, located in C:\Users\Student\AppData\Local\Temp\, the normalized vector will look as follows:

$$e_1 = (4688, 1435, Stud1, launch\ of\ the\ process, Name1.exe, \\ 1(AppData\Local\Temp\), 2025 - 08 - 2802 : 14 : 35) \quad (2)$$

And for the event of an unsuccessful login by user Stud2, the normalized vector will look as follows:

$$e_2 = (4625, -, Stud2, failed\ login, \\ -, 0, 2025 - 08 - 2801 : 05 : 20) \quad (3)$$

4.2. Normalization of events at the network level

Network events, like OS events, reflect user and service activity and may contain signs of a potential threat. Examples of network-level OS security events that can be classified as potential threats include:

- connection from an internal network device to an external IP address, for example, IP address 203.0.113.10 port 22;
- 500 connections per minute from a single IP address;
- HTTP requests /admin or /login from different clients;
- transfer of large amounts of data to a non-standard port;
- remote connection to internal services.

For the above network events, we form the following vector:

$$t_i = (IPsrc, IPdst, port, prot, time) \quad (4)$$

where IPsrc is the IP address of the packet or session source, IPdst is the IP address of the packet or session destination, port is the destination port, prot is the protocol, time is the date and time of the event .

The vector represented by formula 4 covers topological, protocol, temporal, and

statistical connection parameters, which enables the detection of typical network attack techniques (covert communication channels, address space scanning, tunneling, and data exfiltration). An additional advantage is the reduction in the amount of stored information compared to a full dump of network traffic.

For a network event involving an SSH session connection to an external resource from a local network, the vector described by formula 4 will look as follows:

$$t_1 = (192.168.1.10, 203.0.113.10, 22, \\ TCP, 2025 - 08 - 28\ 12 : 10 : 55) \quad (5)$$

The vector showing a student's normal interaction with web resources will be represented as follows:

$$t_1 = (192.168.1.30, 198.51.100.10, 443, \\ TCP, 2025 - 08 - 28\ 14 : 19 : 38) \quad (6)$$

5. Vectorization of normalized events

Normalized information security events must be vectorized, i.e., converted into numerical values using the methods described below. The dimension of normalized vectors will depend on the selected encoding methods; for example, the BERT method can produce up to 768 vector components. During the work, coding methods by feature type presented in Table 1 [14–16, 18] were considered.

Apply the coding features specified in Table 1 for vectorization of normalized events also in the form of vectors described by Form. 1 and 4. Coding methods for os and network events are presented in Tables 2 and 3.

On the basis of Table 2, the vector e_i ,

Table 1: Methods of encoding characteristics.

Feature type	Method	Purpose	Applicability
Categorical	One-Hot Encoding	Simple binary representation of categories	Small number of unique values
	Label Encoding	Replacing categories with indices	Ordered categories
	Target Encoding	Replacing categories with the average value of the target	Classification
	Embedding Encoding	Trainable dense vectors	Large categorical sets
	Hash Encoding	Hash categories into a fixed space	Scalability
Numerical	Min Max Scaling	Scaling in [0,1]	Limited ranges
	Z-score Normalization	Normalization by mean and σ	Approximately normal distribution
	Log Scaling	Compression of exponential distributions	Load indicators, network parameters
	Multi-hot Encoding	Multiple flag representation	TCP flags, indicators
Temporal	Sin/Cos Encoding	Cyclic time encoding	Repeating intervals
	Timestamp Embedding	Trainable temporal embeddings	Sequential models
Text	TF-IDF	Term weighting	Short messages
	Word2Vec / Doc2Vec	Semantic vectors of words and documents	Text logs
	BERT / LogBERT	Contextual embeddings	Deep log analysis
Mixed	Hash / Graph Embedding	Cross-features (IP, MAC)	Network data

Table 2: Encoding methods for normalized OS events.

Field	Description	Data type	Encoding method
EventID	Windows event code	Numeric	One-Hot / Embedding
IDproc	Unique process identifier	Numeric	Min-max normalization
User	Account that initiated the event	Categorical	Label / Embedding
Type	Operation type	categorical	One-Hot
File	Executable file or modifiable resource	text	TF-IDF / BERT embedding
dir	Critical directory flag	binary	0/1
Time	Date and time of the event	temporal	normalization + sine/cosine encoding

Table 3: Encoding methods for normalized network events.

Field	Description	Data type	Encoding method
IPsrc	Source IP address	Numeric	IP?int / Embedding
IPdst	Destination IP address	Numeric	IP?int / Embedding
port	Destination port	Numeric	Min-max normalization
prot	Protocol	categorical	One-Hot
time	Date and time of the event	temporal	normalization + sine/cosine encoding

described by Form. 1, has the following form:

$$v_{OS_i} = (v_{eventID}, v_{ID}, v_{User}, v_{type}, v_{name}, v_{dir}, v_{time}) \quad (7)$$

where v_{OS_i} is the transformed vector e_i described by Form. 1, $v_{eventID}$ is the numerical value of the EventID parameter, v_{ID} is the numerical value of the unique processor identifier, v_{User} is the converted value of the account that initiated the event, v_{type} is the converted value of the operation type, v_{name} is the converted value of the executable file or modifiable resource, v_{dir} is the criticality value of the directory, v_{time} is the converted value of the event date and time.

On the basis of Table 3, the vector t_i , described by Form. 4, has the following form:

$$v_{NET_i} = (v_{ipsrc}, v_{ipdst}, v_{port}, v_{prot}, v_{time}) \quad (8)$$

where v_{NET_i} is the transformed vector t_i described by v , v_{ipsrc} is the transformed value of the source IP address, v_{ipdst} is the transformed value of the destination IP address, v_{port} is the numeric value of the port, v_{prot} is the numeric value of the protocol as defined by IANA, v_{time} is the transformed value of the date and time of the event.

Time-ordered vectors v_{OS_i} and v_{NET_i} are input into architectures such as LSTM, GRU, or Transformer (e.g., LogBERT), which allows patterns and anomalies in user or process activity to be identified [15, 16].

When transferring vectors v_{OS_i} and v_{NET_i} to a DL model, you can use time series of network events (1D-CNN and LSTM to identify activity patterns) or network topologies, such as Graph Neural Networks (GNN), where IP addresses are vertices and events are edges with a vector [17, 18].

Using the cybersecurity event vectors described by Form. 7 and 7, we formulate a problem for finding potential threats using deep learning:

Let $V_i = \{v_{OS_1}, v_{OS_2}, \dots, v_{OS_n}, v_{NET_1}, v_{NET_2}, \dots, v_{NET_{n'}}\}$ event vector, where n and n' are the number of events received during time t_i

from the OS and network. Each event $v_{OS_i} \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is described by a vector according to Form. 7, and event $v_{NET_i} \in \mathbb{R}^{m'}$ is described by a vector according to Form. 8, where m is the dimension of vector v_{OS_i} and m' is the dimension of vector v_{NET_i} . The function that will show whether an OS event or network event is legitimate activity or a potential threat takes the form:

$$\hat{y}_i = f(V_i) \quad (9)$$

where \hat{y}_i is a probability between 0 and 1, where 0 is normal behavior and 1 is a potential threat, V_i event vector over time t_i .

Then the task is formalized as a probabilistic binary classification, where we will use the cross-entropy loss function as the optimization criterion when training the model:

$$L = -\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n [y_i \log(\hat{y}_i) + (1 - y_i) \log(1 - \hat{y}_i)] \quad (10)$$

where $\hat{y}_i = f(x_i)$ is the model prediction, $y_i = 0$ if event i refers to normal behavior and $y_i = 1$ if event i is a potential threat.

The choice of function is driven by the requirement to minimize the information discrepancy between the true and predicted class distributions and ensures stable gradients during training, as well as allowing for natural extension to the case of class imbalance, which is characteristic of tasks related to intrusion detection systems.

6. Explainable deep learning (XAI): Principles and applications

There are two main types of explanations in XAI algorithms [19]:

- Post-hoc explanations applied after model training. These include visualization methods, local analysis, and approximation of a complex model with a simpler one.
- Intrinsic methods designed so that the model itself is interpretable (e.g., using simple architectures or special constraints).

The most popular methods of explainable DL include:

- LIME (Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations) approximates the behavior of a complex model locally, around the object of interest, using a linear model:

$$\arg \min_{g \in G} \mathcal{L}(f, g, \omega_x) + \Omega(g) \quad (11)$$

where f the original nonlinear model mapping the feature space to the response space, g an interpretable surrogate model that locally approximates the behavior of the function f in the neighborhood of the point x , G the set of admissible interpretable models with limited complexity, x the object (data instance) for which a local approximation is constructed, ω_x a proximity weighting function depending on the distance to the point x and defining the local nature of the approximation, $\mathcal{L}(f, g, \omega_x)$ a local discrepancy functional measuring the degree of agreement between the surrogate model g and the nonlinear model f in the neighborhood of the point x , weighted by ω_x , $\Omega(g)$ a regularization functional that constrains the complexity of the model g and ensures its interpretability.

- SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) uses game theory to evaluate the contribution of each feature to the value of the model's final prediction:

$$f(x) = \phi_0 + \sum_{i=1}^d \phi_i \quad (12)$$

where ϕ_0 is the base value that corresponds to the model's average prediction on the training sample and ϕ_i is the contribution of the i -th feature, calculated according to Shapley's principle:

$$\phi_i = \sum_{S \subseteq F \setminus \{i\}} \frac{|S|!(|F| - |S| - 1)!}{|F|!} [f(S \cup i) - f(S)] \quad (13)$$

where F - the set of all features, S - an arbitrary subset of features that does not contain, $f(S)$ - the value of the model when using only features from the set S .

- Grad-CAM (Gradient-weighted Class Activation Mapping) is used to visualize the importance of inputs based on gradients in convolutional networks. The importance of inputs is calculated as follows:

$$L_c = ReLU \left(\sum_k \alpha_k^c A^k \right) \quad (14)$$

where α_k^c is the weight indicating how important the map k is for class c , A^k is the feature map of the k -th channel of the last convolutional layer.

- Attention Mechanisms built-in attention mechanisms in transformers allow you to visualize which input elements are important for the model. The following basic formula is used to calculate importance:

$$Attention(Q, K, V) = \text{softmax} \left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}} \right) V \quad (15)$$

where Q is the query to XAI, K is the characteristics of all input elements, V is the information or value we will receive, QK^T shows how relevant each input element is to the query (here, the scalar product and the upper index T denote a transposed vector), d_k is the dimension of the features in K .

In the context of university IT infrastructure, XAI can be used to [20]:

- explain why traffic was classified as malicious;
- identify the most dangerous users or devices;

- increase the confidence of information security administrators in the model's results;
- formalizing incident reports and automating audits.

Thus, integrating XAI into a higher education institution's security system improves the accuracy of predictions and makes them interpretable and useful for cybersecurity professionals in their decision-making.

7. Information security system architecture based on XAI solution

In the context of higher education IT infrastructure, XAI methods are used to justify the classification of network traffic as malicious, identify the most critical entities or network nodes, increase administrators' confidence in the results of automated analysis, and formalize incident reporting and support internal audit procedures [19].

The introduction of XAI into the cybersecurity framework requires a review of the system architecture, as classic ML models focused exclusively on detection accuracy do not provide traceability and reproducibility of decisions made. Explainability requires a separate layer for generating and storing interpretations, as well as mechanisms for auditing and monitoring degradation. Thus, a new architecture is needed to ensure transparency, regulatory compliance, and risk management when using intelligent protection methods.

The implementation of explainable deep learning into the information infrastructure protection system of a higher education institution requires a comprehensive approach that includes an event processing subsystem, a decision explanation mechanism, and a subsystem for interaction with security administrators [21–24]. The architecture of an information protection system based on an XAI solution for a higher education institution should be modular and

scalable, allowing new data sources and analysis algorithms to be integrated without significant changes. The system proposed in this paper consists of the following components, as shown in Fig. 1 [25, 26]:

1. Devices. This component includes the following modules:
 - data sources, which are network traffic, event logs, activity, etc.;
 - agents that ensure the flow of events from data sources to the management server using Syslog, NetFlow, and pre-installed agents.
2. Preprocessing and storage. This component is responsible for routing, storing, and preprocessing raw data. The management system includes the following modules:
 - a data broker that transmits raw data. The data broker must support multiple sources and, if necessary, provide routing between different system components;
 - storage, which is necessary to save all information for further analysis and investigation of incidents. The data storage module must meet the following requirements: reliability, high search speed, scalability, support for large amounts of data;
 - preprocessing and normalization, converts source information, which may be scattered, non-standardized, and presented in various formats, into a unified, structured form suitable for further analysis. The main task of this module is to ensure the consistency and integrity of incoming data at the preprocessing stage. This module also performs normalization, i.e., converting all input data to a single format, cleaning up information, eliminating duplicate records, empty values, and other elements that may

FIG. 1. Architecture of a malicious activity detection system using deep learning and explainable artificial intelligence.

affect the accuracy of the analysis. The operation of the preprocessing and storage module is described by Form. 1–8.

3. Expertise. This component is responsible for detecting malicious or suspicious activity based on information received from the pre-processing and storage components and consists of the following modules:

- a knowledge base, which is a structured repository of information

about threat types, events, attack techniques, analysis rules, and response actions;

- User and Entity Behavior Analytics (UEBA) module, which analyzes user and device behavior to identify anomalies and suspicious activities;
- machine learning, which learns from labeled data to classify events and detect threats based on time series, patterns, or anomalies in the data.

4. Visualization and response. This

component is responsible for providing information in a readable form to the system user, and also includes responding to information security events and explaining why the presented data set is a threat to information security. The visualization and response component consists of the following modules:

- XAI, which provides interpretation of machine learning model decisions and allows you to understand why the system classified an event as a threat;
- the administrator panel, which is an interface for the response specialist with graphs, alerts, and explanations, and helps to respond and make decisions as quickly as possible;
- response, which allows you to automatically block and/or restrict access to a user or device using integration with the university's information and communication structure.

Integrating XAI methods into a university's information security system improves threat detection accuracy and increases trust in automated decisions. In an educational environment, where transparency and justification of actions are particularly important, the system's ability to justify its conclusions becomes a key factor in its practical value.

8. Conclusion

The paper considers the problem of detecting undesirable information security events at the OS level and analyzes XAI methods applicable to cybersecurity tasks. Based on the data generated by the OS, methods for normalizing and vectorizing information security events are proposed, whereby the resulting vectors are subsequently sent to a DL model to identify potential threats and explain them using XAI. While maintaining the existing cybersecurity system of the higher education institution, the proposed new system architecture, which includes an XAI module, is focused on comprehensive processing of OS events, from anomaly detection to providing the operator with reasonable and reproducible conclusions. The advantages of the developed approach are increased transparency of decision-making, reduced operational risks, and expanded audit capabilities while maintaining high threat detection accuracy. Prospects for further research are related to the experimental testing of the architecture and the qualitative and quantitative assessment of its effectiveness in real operating conditions.

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